

Concept of Child Labour

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ABSTRACT

Child labourers are exploited, exposed to hazardous work conditions and paid a pittance for their long hours of work. Forced to forego education, shouldering responsibilities far beyond their years, becoming worldly-wise when their peers have yet to leave the cocoons of parental protection, these children never know what childhood is. The Indian Constitution enshrines that no child below the age of 14 years shall be employed to work in any factory or in any hazardous employment (Article 24). Childhood and youth are to be protected against exploitation and against moral and material abandonment (Article 39). The state shall endeavor to provide within a period of 10 years from the commencement of the Constitution free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of 14 years (Article 45).

Keywords: Abandonment, Hazardous employment, Children, Childhood, Exploited

Incidence of Child Labour in India

Of the total population of 1,029 million in 2001, about 364 million (35.35%) were children below the age of 14 years. Those in the age group of 5-14 years were about 256 million (or 24.60%) (Premi, 2011: 79-80). There is thus a perceptible decline in the proportion of children in the age group years from 1971 onwards, mainly due to decline in birth rates. Although the number of child labor globally has declined by one - third since 2000 - from 246 million to 168 million - it is not enough to achieve the goal of eliminating the worst forms of child labor by 2016 agreed by the international community through the International Labor Organization (ILO) Millions of children from poor families are still compelled by economic considerations to join the labor force. A new ILO report, Making Program Against Child Labor (2013) says that the largest absolute number of child labourers is found in the Asia-Pacific region (almost 78 million), but Sub-Saharan Africa continues to be the region with the highest incidence. of child labor in terms of proportion of the population, at over 21 percent. Incidence of child labor is highest in poorer countries but middle-income countries have the largest numbers of child labourers. Child labor amount Agriculture remains by far the most important sector where child labourers girls fell by 40 per cent since 2000, compared 25 per cent for boys found 98 million children, or 59 %), but the problems are not negl can be gible in services (54 million) and industry (12 million) - mostly in the informal economy Between 2008 and 2012, child labor among children aged 5-17 years declined in Asia and the Pacific, Latin American and the Caribbean and Sub-Saharan Africa regions. Asia and the Pacific registered by far the largest decline, from 114 million in 2008 to 78 million in 2012. The number of child laborers also decreased in Sub-Saharan Africa (by 6 million), and modestly in Latin America and the Caribbean (by 1.6 million). There are 9.2 million child laborers in the Middle East and North Africa. In India, as per the 2001 Census, there were 12.60 million working children in the age group of 5-14 years as compared to 11.30 million in 1991 revealing an increasing trend in absolute numbers though the work participation rates of children (5-14) has come down from 5.4 percent during 1991 to 5 percent during 2001. The recent round of the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) estimates suggests that the child labor in the country is around 8.9 million in 2004-05 with a workforce participation rate of 3.4 percent. However, due to definitional problems, a substantial proportion of child labor may remain uncounted. Census data further shows that there is a decline in the absolute number as well as the percentage of

main workers of children (5-14 to total population in that age group from 4.3% in 1991 to 2.3% in 2001). But there was a substantial increase in marginal workers in every category of workers, irrespective of sex and residence. As a result, despite the number of main workers declining from 9.08 million in 1991 to 5.78 million in 2001, the total number of children in the workforce increased. A large part of the increase was accounted for by the increase in marginal workers, which increased from 2.2 million in 1991 to 6.89 million in 2001. Main and marginal workers put together, the work participation rate (WPR) of children in the 5-14 age group has declined from 5.4 percent during 1991 to 5 percent in 2001. The trends between 1991 and 2001 of declining main child workers along with increasing marginal workers may indicate the changing nature of work done by children. There is a general trend of marginalization of labor force in the country and this is also reflected in the census figures. This is to be seen in the context of decelerating employment growth in general in the economy during the last decade that is characterized as an era of globalization. The first Act to regulate the employment of children and their hours of work was the Factory Act of 1881. A commission was appointed in 1929 to Minimum age of child employment. On its recommendation Child Labor Act, 1933 was passed prohibiting employment of children below 14 years of age. The Factory Act of 1948 provided some safeguards to child labourers. In 1986, the parliament enacted the Child Labor A Regulation and Prohibition), prohibiting the employment of children certain jobs and regulating the conditions of work in hazardous The Juvenile Justice Act, 1986 which superseded the existing Children's Act in different states and union territories and came into force from October 1987, provides for the creation of Advisory Boards and the establishment State Children Funds for preventing the abuse of children, for the protection and care of children, for the mobilization of resources and for the provision facilities for education, training and rehabilitation of the neglected children But, in spite of all these measures, children continue to be employed, harassed and abused.

Nature of Child Work

Thus, India has the largest number of child workers in the world. They are employed in many industries and trades, including garments, footwear, brick kilns, stainless steel, hotels and textile shops. Many work in export-oriented hazardous industries like carpet weaving, gem polishing, glass blowing firecrackers units, match works, brassware, electro-plating, lead mining, stone quarrying, lock-making and beady-rolling, and in tea gardens. In addition,

nearly 85 percent of child labourers in India are hard-to-reach,¹ invisible and excluded, as they work largely in the unorganized sector, both rural and urban, within the family or in household-based units, which are generally out of the purview of labor laws. According to an ILP report on child labor in India, based on 2001 census, the distribution of total workforce aged 5-14 years in different industry categories at all-India level shows that the maximum number of children (ie, 48%) are employed in manufacturing sector, followed by agriculture, hunting, forestry and fishing (20%), and wholesale/retail trade (10%). The number of children in urban areas, who work in restaurants and canteens, or those engaged in picking rags and hawking goods, is vast but unrecorded. And, among the more unfortunate ones are those who are employed in hazardous industries like fireworks and match box units. According to a study conducted by the National Commission for Protection of Children Rights (2013), approximately 70 per cent firecrackers and matches produced in India are from Sivakasi. In 2011, Sivakasi was home to over 9,500 firecracker factories and produced almost 90 percent of total fireworks and match factories fulfilling 75 percent demand of matches in the country. Tamil Nadu has been in limelight for long in terms of its child labor problem where innocent children fall prey to the exploitative labor firecrackers and match industries. Every year, there occur many fire accidents in these units in which a number of labourers, including children, die. Mostly children in the age group of 5-15 work for more than 12 hours a sa piecerate basis day and earn paltry sum as wages.² They are generally paid on a which is very low and thus they are indirectly forced to work faster and longer affecting their health and nutrition. Most of the children are ignorant of the benefits of education which include decent living without any damage to their health and development. There are also health consequences. Asthma, eye infection and TB are prevalent among 90 percent of children who are involved in gun powder filling and are directly in contact with the chemical ingredients of crackers and matches. These workers usually do not wear any protective clothes and their whole skins are normally covered by the chemicals such as sulphur, aluminium powder and gun powder. Similarly, in a study report on children in Indian carpet industry, commissioned by the International Labor Rights Fund, it is found that children account for 7.13 percent of the total workforce. Most of the children (82%) working on looms are boys, and the majority (58%) of them belong to the labor families. Not only

¹ Bandura, A., *Aggression: A Social Learning Analysis*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1973.

² Bandura, A., *Aggression: A Social Learning Analysis*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1973.

this, the proportion of child labor to the workforce is higher in the Persian variety of carpets. Although, according to the study, compared to the 1990s, there has been a decline in the magnitude of child labor in the carpet industry, but this is not to the extent of claims made by the government and industry sources. The surveys of the metropolitan and mega cities make shocking revelations, Mumbai has the largest number of child labourers. Even in Delhi, more than one lakh children work in dhabas, tea stalls and restaurants on a daily wage of Rs 50 or Rs 100. In the mining sector, about half of the workers are children below 15. In most cases, children are favored as they are docile and hence can be exploited. Child labor is inextricably linked to bonded labor. In Andhra Pradesh, 21 percent of the bonded labourers are under sixteen. In Karnataka, 10.3 per cent and in Tamil Nadu 8.7 per cent belong to this age group. A study shows that at the time of entering bondage, many labourers are as young as five years old. In Odisha, one common way of clearing debt is to sell daughters, 8 to 10 years old, as maid servants, to the creditor. In several parts of the country, bonded fathers, over 40 years old, free themselves their sons into bondage, In the tea gardens of Assam, where employment of children below 12 years is prohibited, girls who bring food to their working mothers are an important role to play in mining operations. While men do the dig encouraged to stay back and help with the work. Children, mostly boys, have inside the pits, boys carry coal to the surface. Children below 12 are preferred because their height allows them to walk without bending in the Preference for child workers is most common in the unorganized because here it is relatively easy for employers to circumvent laws. Children are concealed from factory inspectors during inspection, their ages are arbitrarily to make them eligible for employment, or those eligible for a wages are denied their legitimate share because the employers lower them in the forms.

Causes of Child

Labor in a country like India where one in five persons is living, below poverty line child labor is a complex issue. Children work out of necessity and without their earnings (however meagre they may be), a family cannot survive. A large number of them do not even have families or cannot count on them for support. In these circumstances, the alternative to work may be idleness, education, or worse, crime. Employers give certain justifications for employing children to suppress their guilt feelings. They say that the work keeps children away from starvation. They are prevented from committing crimes which they would have

indulged in if they had no jobs.³ The bureaucrats hold that the total eradication of child labour is not feasible because the government cannot provide substantial alternative employment to them. The social scientists say that the main cause of child labour is poverty. The children either supplement their parents' income or are the only wage earners in the family. According to Planning Commission of India's poverty estimates for 2011-12, released in July 2013, 21.9 percent of the total population of India or about 270 million people live below the poverty line. Of these, 217 million (25.7%) are living in rural areas and 53 million (13.7%) in urban areas. The highest number of persons living below the poverty line are found in Uttar Pradesh (5.98 crore), followed by Bihar (3.58 crore), Madhya Pradesh (2.34 crore) and Maharashtra (1.98 crore). These persons are forced to send their children to work in factories, etc. Another reason is that child labour is deliberately created by vested interests to get cheap labour. The third reason forwarded for the existence of child labour is that it benefits industries, such as the carpet industry, which earns crores of rupees in foreign exchange by exporting.

Working Conditions of Child Labourers

Children work in dangerously polluted factories whose brick walls are scarred with soot (black powder in smoke) and there is an oppressive smell in the air. Hardon occupations / processes which are covered under the Child (Prohibition & Regulation) Act, Le. 18 occupations and 65 However, as per survey conducted by National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) in 2004-05, the number of working children is estimated at lakh. It shows that the efforts of the government have borne the desired for Over the years, the Government of India has multiplied its effort address the needs and rights of exploited children. Way back in 1929, Central Government formed the first committee called Gurupadn Committee to study the issue of child labour and to suggest measures to tackle it. The Committee examined the problem in detail and made far-reaching recommendations. It observed that as long as poverty continues it would be difficult to totally eliminate child labour and hence, any attempt to abolish it through legal recourse would not be a practical proposition. The Committee felt that in the circumstances, the only alternative left was to a child labor in hazardous areas and to regulate and ameliorate the conditions of work in other

³ Bolton, F.G. and Bolton, S.R., Working with Violent Families, Sage Publications, New York, 1987.

areas. It recommended that a multiple policy approach is required in dealing with the problems of working children. Based on the recommendations of Gurupadaswamy Committee, the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act was enacted in 1986. The Act prohibits employment of children in certain specified hazardous occupation and processes and regulates the working conditions in others. The list hazardous occupations and processes is progressively being expanded on the recommendation of Child Labour Technical Advisory Committee constituted under the Act. In consonance with the above approach, a National Policy on Child Labour was formulated in 1987.⁴ The policy seeks to adopt a gradual & sequential approach with a focus on rehabilitation of children working in hazardous occupations and processes in the first instance. The Action Plan outlined in the policy for tackling this problem is as follows: Legislative action plan for strict enforcement of Child Labour Act and other labour laws to ensure that children are not employed in hazardous employments, and that the working conditions of child working in non - Hazardous areas are regulated in accordance with the provisions of the Child Labor Act. It also entails further identification of additional occupations and processes, which are detrimental to the health and safety of the children. Focusing on general developmental programs for benefiting child labour: As poverty is the root cause of child labour, the action plan emphasizes the need to cover these children and their families under various poverty alleviation and employment generation schemes of the government. They work near furnaces which burn at a temperature of 1400-1500 centigrade they handle dangerous chemicals like arsenic and potassium. They work glass blowing units where the work exerts their lungs and creates diseases like tuberculosis among the working children; many are the main or major wage earners in the family who always remain worried about feeding their dependents the gigantic child workers whose parents live in some far off city or village are really in despair. Some work for 9 to 10 hours including night shifts. Even when the factories are fully functional, they are paid not more than Rs 3,000 per month, all of which they hand over to their guardians who do not give them even a rupee a day for tea during the night shift. There are times when their bodies ache, minds fog, hearts cry, spirits bleed, but on orders of the employer they work for 10 to 11 hours at a stretch visit to several factories in Delhi, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh and Maharashtra reveals that a large number of child workers have sunken chests and thin bone

⁴Burgess, R.L., "Child Abuse: A Social Interactional Analysis", in Ben Lahey and Alan Kazdin (eds), Advances in Clinical Child Psychology, Vol. 2, Plenum Press, New York, 1979.

frames which give them a fragile look. They look like rag dolls, limp, unwashed and scraggy. They wear coarse and bailily tailored clothes. Many of them have scabies on hands, arms and legs.⁵ The heads of a few are tonsured probably because the skin on their skull has developed severe infection A large number of the child workers are virtually confined in small rooms under inhuman conditions and in the most unhygienic surroundings. Most of these children come from extremely poor households. They are either school drop-outs or have not seen any school at all. They earn a very meagre wage and work in most unsafe conditions. The hazardous conditions take their toll. Children suffer from lung diseases, tuberculosis, eye diseases, asthma, bronchitis and backaches. Some are injured in fire accidents. Many become unemployable even at the age of 20, 11 injured or incapacitated, they are discarded mercilessly by their employers

Ameliorating Child Labour in India

The problem of child labour continues to pose a big challenge before the nation. The government has been taking various pro-active measures to tackle this problem. However, considering the magnitude and extent of the problem that it is essentially a socio-economic problem inextricably linked to poverty and illiteracy, it requires concerted efforts from all sections of the problem. society to make a dent in According to the Census 2001 figures there are 1.26 crore working children in the age group of 5-14 as compared to the total child population of 25.2 crore. There are approximately 12 lakh children working in the Project based plan of action envisages starting of projects in areas of high concentration of child labour. Pursuant to this, in 1988, the National Child Labour Project (NCL) scheme was launched in sine districts of high child labour endemicity in the entry. The scheme envisages running of special schools for child labour withdrawn from work. In the special schools, these children receive formal/non-formal education along with provided stipend of Rs.150 per month, supplementary nutrition and regular health check ups so as to prepare them to join regular mainstream schools. Under the scheme, funds are given to the District Collectors for running special schools for child labour. Most of these schools are run by the NGOs in the district. In January 2005, the NCLP scheme has been expanded to 250 districts in 21 different Indian states, covering 42 percent of all districts of the country. Thus, the

⁵ Elmer, E., Children in Jeopardy: A Study of Abused Minors and Their Families, University of Pittsburgh Press, Pittsburgh, 1967.

governments have accordingly been taking proactive steps to tackle this problem through strict enforcement of legislative provisions along with simultaneous rehabilitative measures. State Governments, which are the appropriate implementing authorities, have been conducting regular inspections and raids to detect cases of violations. Since poverty is the root cause of this problem, and enforcement alone cannot help solve it, the governments have been laying a lot of emphasis on the rehabilitation of these children and improving the economic conditions of their families. The Supreme Court too, in a significant judgment, given on December 10, 1996, while disposing of public interest litigation by one lawyer, aimed at preventing exploitation of children and safeguarding their economic, social and humanitarian rights, banned child labour on hazardous jobs and ordered the setting up of a Child Labour Rehabilitation Welfare Fund. The offending employer would have to deposit Rs 20,000 as compensation for each child in the fund.⁶ The apex court made it clear that the liability of the employer would not cease even if he now desired to disengage the child. The court gave comprehensive directions to central and state governments to see that an adult member of the child's family gets a job in lieu of the child's employment. However, realizing the strain on the resources of the state, the court did not allow the government to ensure alternative employment in every case of the child labourer. Instead, the appropriate government would be required to deposit Rs 5,000 in the fund for each child employed in a factory or mine or any other hazardous employment (The Hindustan Times, December 11, 1996). The apex court also directed the concerned states to conduct a survey on children within six months, for which the court identified nine industries with primary cases of child labor employers. These industries were : match industry in Sivakasi, Tamil; polishing industry in Gujarat precious stone polishing industry, Jaipur, Rajasthan; glass industry Firozabad, brassware industry in Moradabad and the handicraft industry in Mirzapur-Bhadoi, lock making industry in Aligarh-all Pradesh; slate industry in Markapur, Andhra Pradesh, and slate Mandsaur, Madhya Pradesh. The Supreme Court said that the given or payment made would cease if the child is not sent for educating the parents. The court warned of penal action in case of non-compliance with the directive. In the context of non-hazardous jobs, the court directed the appropriate authority to see that the working hours of the child do not exceed four to six hours a day and at least two hours are set aside daily for the child's

⁶ Gelles, R.J. and Cornell, C.P., Intimate Violence in Families, Sage Publications, Beverly Hills, 1985.

education. It would also ensure that the entire cost of education was borne by the employer. range industry employee.

An Evaluation

Despite the hope aroused of some improvement in the lot of the child workers, the enactment of the Child Labor (Prohibition and Regulation Act, 1986, has not goaded either the state governments or the Centre to sort of purposive action even on a limited front. Nothing illustrates the apathy as the fate of the plan of action announced by the Labour Ministry in August 1987 as an essential Policy of the National Labour. Child Of the ten projects drawn up under the plan to enforce the Act and provide welfare inputs in such vulnerable areas as the glass industry in Firozabad, carpet weaving industry in Mirzapur, diamond polishing industry in Surat and match industry in Sivakasi, only one has been taken up on experimental basis. Considering that this lone project in the match industry is an ongoing one that has since been dovetailed into the action plan, the action of the policy as such has achieved nothing beyond delineating the responsibility of the states and the Centre.⁷ If this is the fate of a pillar scheme devised to benefit just 30,000 of the 17 million child labour force, the lot of the rest covered by the Act will be numbers slogging for a pittance in the unorganized sector, who are outside the ambit no better than that of the vastly greater purview of the Act. The idea behind formulating the action plan apparently was to make a beginning with the implementation of the new law and related provisions of other legislations affecting children in such sectors where the incidence of child labor is quite endemic. The failure of the projects to taste off inspires no hope about the success of the plan to shift the thrust of the anti-poverty programs to those segments of society that contribute the bulk of child workers to this extent, the enactment of the legislation may have proven ineffective in affording a measure of protection to children forced to earn.

Conclusion

The study of the rising neural impoverishment and the struggle once in urban areas. The legislation was drafted on the sand premise that with the root cause of poverty cannot be eliminated overnight, the pragmatic approach was to regulate the practice of child labour.

⁷ Gelles, R.J., "Child Abuse as Psychopathology: A Sociological Critique and Reformulation", American Journal of Ortho. Psychiatry, Vol. 43, July, 1973.

Accordingly, employment of children below 14 years has been allowed in selected areas of the non-hazardous organized sector, with suitable safeguards against their exploitation and provision for educational and recreational facilities. A serious omission in the legislation relates to the enforcement machinery, the flexibility of which has enabled employers to circumvent the provisions of the law with impunity. Even if punishment for the violation of the new law has been made stiffer, the cheap, flexible and non-complaining labor provided by children creates a vested interest in perpetuating the practice. In the absence of an efficient and rigorous inspection machinery, nothing prevents the employers from flouting the legal provisions in the full knowledge that the accused workers themselves will become willing accomplices in covering it up. Another lacuna in the Act is the failure to define what constitutes hazardous jobs, while the committee set up to identify permissible jobs has not made much progress. The only way to ensure compliance with the Act is to make punishment for violations more stringent and incorporate a provision for surprise checks and establish a separate vigilance cell. With regard to the workers' interest, it should be made mandatory for all employers to take steps for the intellectual, vocational and educational well-being and upliftment of a child worker, whether one is employed as a factory hand, a domestic servant or a shop assistant. In this context, the impact of policies which may not be specifically addressed to children but which try to alleviate poverty and inequality can have a significant and even decisive impact. Such policies may include agrarian reforms, employment generation schemes, dissemination of improved technology among the poor, promotion of the informal sector and creation of cooperatives and social security programs. Laws and regulations must be backed by effective enforcement machinery. This calls for the strengthening of labour inspection and related services. In order to facilitate the verification of an effective system of birth registration should be maintained by the public authorities. It should be made mandatory for employers to maintain registers and documents indicating the names and ages of all the employed children. That children have to work is sad, but that they should work in conditions dangerous to their health and safety is totally unacceptable. Nor can the problem of child labour be left untackled until economic conditions and social structures are fundamentally improved.

Toiling long hours for a pittance, these little breadwinners accept exploitation as a way of life. They only know their sorrows. Silent acceptance is writ large on their faces. Each day adds more to their growing numbers. Although it is true that labour helps children in

their survival, should the children be made to pay for the government's inability to provide alternative employment or inability to curb poverty? Should they be forced to inhabit an adult world, bear adult responsibilities, and suffer abysmal exploitation? The child workers have no shelter, no food and no education. They run the risk of contracting various ailments and skin diseases. They are vulnerable to exploitation by almost anyone - the employer, the parents, the cops, and even the common man. They become easy targets of drug pushers. They are even sexually abused. Certain principles of policy are, therefore, to be followed by the state so that children get opportunities to develop in a healthy manner and in conditions of freedom and dignity and the childhood and youth are protected against exploitation and moral and material abandonment. Let us hope, by the orders and the directions of the Supreme Court in December 1996, and the measures taken by the state, the child of the century will find himself/herself into the "heaven of freedom"

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